

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Le Texier**FIRST NAME:** Sylvain**PROGRAM CODE:** DIDOL**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (author-date)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

ACADEMIC WRITING AS A CHALLENGE

1) INTRODUCTION

The quality of academic papers requires attention and time. The first course materials in ACA-401D provide a range of information regarding the formatting, the spelling and the norms that I need to adopt. I was formerly a student using American Psychological Association reference (APA) with European conventions. Thus, the current course can give me a new approach focusing on a quality-driven academic writing. The structure of the course allows improving my skills in writing but even questioning my way to progress. Therefore, I think that the efforts given to this course will benefit the quality of my writing and reinforce my hope to follow an academic career.

2) A FIELD OF NORMS

Academic writings follow clear and precise norms. The purpose of these codes is to provide clarity and avoid ambiguity for readers. Compliance with the standards of academic writing will help to build a path and achieve a specific goal. As a certified teacher and sports enthusiast, I often compare the work of a scholar to a high-level athlete's effort. Indeed, the scholar and the athlete must make use of discipline and precision in the tasks to perform. To do this, they must regularly prepare upstream without rushing to avoid obstacles and achieve their goals. Both must be able to manage their efforts within constraints. Therefore, each step must be well analysed. The course materials ACA-401D provide guidelines to understand how to make use of norms properly. Since the learning of codes may take some time, the course materials advise the readers to start early and to construct an initial plan (EUCLID 2019). This step will allow thinking more in-depth about the contents and the flow of the writing.

Furthermore, there is a world of norms and standards to be integrated and respected. These standards or codes help each student to lead himself in his study plan. Rules are indeed useful for the students because they can understand where they are moving. In addition, these standards have to follow the accuracy of the sources. Turabian notes that the “first obligation as a researcher is to cite your sources accurately and fully so that your readers can find them” (Turabian 2007, 88). These norms of punctuations or quotations have the advantage of being recognized internationally through different official schools such as Harvard Referencing or APA Referencing. Thus, misunderstandings can be avoided, and communication facilitated. Scholars will be able to dialogue through, for example, international conferences or seminars on scientific reports. The uniformity of the standards of academic writing makes it possible to advance debates and research.

The academic standards and codes of writing to be used are well explained in the EUCLID's coursepack (EUCLID 2019). During my previous studies, I was asked to use different academic writing rules of style and most of the time APA. In the course material, it is pointed out that the Turabian style is highly recommended and I never worked with it before. Moreover, living in Europe, the use of British English standards has been more frequent when I was writing previous academic essays. However, a summary of the differences between British and American English is discussed in the course material. It will help me to update my knowledge if I aim to use the American spelling. An interesting point described in the coursepack is about the use of commas with conjunctions. This point does not seem to be so easy to handle. The course material emphasizes that “this issue generates many questions, so the practice of including the comma should be promoted” (EUCLID 2019, 20). The regular training of using the codes is thus a way to be better in academic writing.

3) **A STRICT TRAINING**

An academic text that brings flow and clarity can only be done through regular and rigorous training. As a top athlete, performance can only improve with a varied workout and regular practice which requires a wide range of knowledge. One of them is the ability to vary the sources of the documents. The quality of the academic writings also depends on the chosen materials. This variety will allow opening a more creative and critical thinking because there will be the possibilities to compare different theories. It is thus useful to identify the sources accurately. Turabian lists a couple of advice when choosing the sources and how they will then be embedded in the bibliography (Turabian 2007, 83–89). The more reliable the sources are, the more trustworthy the sources are in the essay. Besides, finding sources of good quality is only a step before making an academic writing of good quality. It is necessary to use quotations from the sources in order to give credits for the work. As stated by Turabian, “research is hard work” (Turabian 2007, 260) and linking quotations from a source of good quality and the flow of an academic essay require a high level of skill.

When facing with a multitude of documents and sources, avoiding any form of plagiarism is meaningful. As EUCLID warns, plagiarism is strictly forbidden, which can lead to a conviction. EUCLID reminds that plagiarism “is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID

2019, 5). As a teacher, plagiarism is an issue which occurs frequently. Many students do not understand the concept of “copyright”. Besides, some of the students get used to copy websites with no knowledge of the source of the sites. Moreover, plagiarism is not only the act of literally copying an author's words, but it can be the process of paraphrasing. Danvivath and Pinjaroenpan (2017) investigated the level of plagiarism and paraphrasing among Thai students with results revealing that errors were frequent. They could observe that “78% of the students had copied more than 50% of the original words, which subsequently led to a low level of textual transformation as principally required when paraphrasing” (Pinjaroenpan and Danvivath 2017). This last observation shows how paraphrasing and plagiarism has to be mentioned early in the process of academic writing.

The sources can be explored in a variety of database through different languages. I recently noticed that documents in other languages than English might bring a new way of critical thinking and a broader distance on the topics. One explanation could be the theory mentioned by Sapir and Whorf about the impact of the language on thought (Widhiarso 2009). The theory, often referred to the *Sapir-Whorf hypothesis*, underlines that the language may give a different angle of interpretations in particular regarding one's environment. Furthermore, I sometimes read the same topics in the same language, which often referred to the same sources. Reading documents from different languages can thus open new pathways to see further key issues for an essay. However, it is essential to respect academic standards when quoting in a foreign language if this is required. EUCLID gives some example of how to use different spellings from foreign languages and “various jargons” (EUCLID 2019, 32–34). Besides, the use of abbreviation in Latin in academic writing follows strict rules which I am not so familiar with. Thus, I have learnt that Latin abbreviations are more used in informal writing, such as footnotes or bibliography. The English equivalent is preferably used in everyday language (EUCLID 2019, 56).

4) **GOOD TOOLS FOR GOOD RESULTS**

Using good tools to write an academic paper is a necessity. A scholar with reliable and efficient tools will be able to provide essays in a higher quality. Thus, EUCLID suggests useful tools to organize the bibliography with Zotero. I have never heard before about Zotero and I feel I still need to train on Zotero before mastering it. So far, I think that Zotero is quite useful for my organisation. The course materials also introduce database research and name some of them: JSTOR, QUESTIA and SSRN. Unfortunately, some of them require subscriptions or fee. However, national databases from European libraries are often free to access and give the opportunity to navigate through current research online. Thus, the British Library through the database ETHOS¹ gives access to PhD dissertations which are not yet published. On the other hand, I am more familiar with the following database: ERUDIT, BASE and ISIDORE. These databases allow searching in different languages and they are linked to newsletters from several European departments so I can be updated about conferences.

The results or opinions mentioned in an academic paper must be able to be debated. The quality of discussions supported by tools such as quotations, citations and sources

1 See <https://ethos.bl.uk/Home.do>.

depend on the investigation made. Self-criticism from one's work is also essential because it allows an openness to observation and scientific criticism. Turabian asserts thus that “if a source seems important or challenges your position, read it a second time slowly and more critically” (Turabian 2007, 92). It is worth reading at least twice the chosen sources so no misunderstandings may come up which could make debates more complicated. I have already written essays with contradictions in my main idea. This feeling is somehow strange but recurring. A good step to avoid this step is probably to ask someone else to read the essay or to wait a few days before rereading one's essay. Both the material course and Turabian recommend taking notes on paper. These notes can work as a line to follow in the flow of ideas and texts.

Besides, the flow of the blocks in an essay is an essential tool when keeping the attention of the readers. Indeed, flow is often associated with a logical sequence of reasoning. Therefore, it is important to use logical connectors. The connectors help to assemble arguments but even to make some evidence in light. Turabian explains that “readers must be able to recognize the order you choose” (Turabian 2007, 147). Thus, drafting the paper may develop productive habits and make me more comfortable. I usually list my ideas on a draft sheet in order to see them visually and to be able to chain a logical suite. It is often necessary to rework paragraphs to eliminate weariness in blocks and especially repetition, what I call the anaphora effect. Hence, the flow of a scientific paper can be compared to a middle-distance race in which each step will provide efficient

5) **CONCLUSION**

Writing academic papers require regular training and a complete practice of the norms. In the course material ACA-401D, I found a couple of explanations and descriptions of these norms. As mentioned above, I used to write academic essays by suing APA with the British spelling. Thus, I have learnt new points through the course material and the Turabian formatting. Since the rules of formatting are quite extensive, I think that it takes some time to integrate all of them. The upcoming response papers are an excellent opportunity to put them into practice. Furthermore, the tools to find for documents such as SSRN and tools to format the papers such as Zotero seem to be worth to explore. Indeed, they can help to make my academic papers more useful for critical thinking and comparing points of views. To my mind, writing an academic essay requires the same efforts than an athlete: *no pain, no gain*.

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